

Effect of Staff Development Programmes on Gender of Teachers for Self Efficacy in Upper Basic Education in Makurdi

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Abstract

In this study, the effect of gender on staff development programmes for self efficacy of teachers in upper basic education in Makurdi local government area of Benue State was examined. Two research questions were raised and answered and two hypotheses formulated and tested. A Questionnaire on Staff Development Programmes and Self-efficacy to Teaching (QSDPSET) was used as the instrument for data collection from 168 teachers drawn from 42 sampled schools (20 public and 24 private) across Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue state. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance. From the results of study, it was revealed that there is a significant influence of staff development programmes on male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. Findings further showed that there is a significant influence of staff development programmes on teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. Overall, the study posits that staff development enhances teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching irrespective gender. Based on these results, it was recommended among others that state and federal Governments, non-governmental organizations, proprietors of schools and other educational stakeholders should regularize the conduct of educational conferences, workshops; seminars etc. for upper basic school teachers.

Keywords: Gender, Staff Development, Self Efficacy, Upper Basic, Education

Introduction

Teachers are the mainstay of the education as he/she promotes teaching/learning process (Yawe, 2004). The role played by teachers in the educational system with specific regards to curriculum planning, curriculum implementation, and evaluation cannot be over emphasised. The effectiveness of teachers in discharging these duties has cumulative effects on overall attainment of generalized education goals and

objectives. Hence, effectiveness of teachers in discharging these statutory responsibilities is dependent on factors such as the teachers' level of education, level of motivation, nature of school leadership provided, teaching/learning environment provided and more importantly, training and development programmes provided by schools to enhance teachers' capacity (Ayodele, Aina & Omotayo, 2018).

According to Ayodele, Aina and Omotayo (2018), teachers are assumed to have been well trained and equipped with adequate knowledge and expertise needed to perform their job effectively. However, educational system operates within a constantly changing and dynamic social system; teachers must be updated in expertise and effectiveness skills through staff development programmes in order to keep them abreast of the dynamism of the system in which they function. Therefore, when teachers lack appropriate professional development and skills to do their job better teaching and learning cannot be effective. To teach effectively, teachers need access to ongoing teacher professional development (Obineme, 2020).

Staff development is a process of behavioural modification or moulding of workers in order to integrate organizational needs with their characteristics (Ayodele, Aina & Omotayo, 2018). It is a process of training staff to improve their skills for better performance. It also refers to skills and knowledge attained for both personal development and career advancement. Iyunade (2017) defined staff professional development as that component of any educational system concerned with the education and training of teachers to acquire the necessary competencies and skills in teaching for improvement in the quality of teachers in the school system. Staff development programmes are training programmes planned to facilitate the learning of job related knowledge, skills and behaviour by employees.

Training can be conducted on or off the job for teachers. On the job training is referred to as in-service training. In service training is defined as job related instruction and educational experiences and activities designed to improve the knowledge and skills of teachers and the quality of services, especially the instructional practice (Curriah, 2016). It is usually geared towards acquisition of knowledge, skills, and behaviours that improve an employees' ability to meet changes in job requirements.

Through staff development programmes, teachers learn new teaching strategies to improve the quality of instruction. However, Darling-Hammond, Hyler, Gardner (2017) posit that effective professional development is structured on professional learning which results in changes to teacher knowledge and practices, and improvements in student learning outcomes. This allows them make changes in the way they teach their students and incorporating innovative teaching methods in the classroom. Some of the training programmes, according to Adi, Agbe, Odeh and Tyokyaa (2019) and Musa (2016), are in-service, conference, workshop, seminars and mentoring. The various staff development programmes are expected to improve teachers' self-efficacy in the teaching.

Moreover, teachers' self-efficacy may relate to gender (Odoh, & Okeofu, 2020; Ogheneakoke & Akpochafo, 2015). Gender refers to ways in which social and cultural factors shape the reality and sense of human identity. It is a social category of shared meaning of characteristics of male and female (Odey, 2017). Gender, according to Makama (2013) is a varied socially and culturally constructed roles, qualities

and behaviour that are ascribed to men and women of different societies. This implies that 'gender' is attributed roles, qualities or features given to men and women of different sociological and cultural entities.

Gender stereotype may influence the choice of staff development programmes. Staff professional development programmes foster the development of self-efficacy in both male and female teachers because they provide the framework within which teachers may get clear information about the outcomes and pattern of progress they are making as they strive to master new knowledge and skill sets. This information is the substance from which strong efficacy beliefs are built. Karabiyik and Korumaz (2014) found in their study that there is a significant positive relationship between male and female teachers' self-efficacy perceptions and staff development programme. Karimi (2011) reported that Staff professional development programme created some belief in the teachers' capabilities and was compelling enough to significantly disrupt the teachers' previous beliefs in their abilities irrespective of gender. Odanga, Raburu and Aloka's (2020) study reported no significant influence of gender on teachers' self-efficacy. However, male teachers have higher self-efficacy in classroom management than their female counterparts. Furthermore, in another study Karabiyik and Korumaz (2014) reported that, females present higher self-efficacy than males regarding the influence of professional staff development programmes. It is against background that this study seeks to examine the effect of staff development programmes on gender of teachers for self efficacy in upper basic education in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. How would staff development programmes influence male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education?
2. What is the influence of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant of staff development programmes on male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education.
2. There is no significant of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education.

Research Methods

This study adopted the survey design. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Questionnaire on Staff Development Programmes and Self-efficacy to Teaching (QSDPSET). The QSDPSET was administered to 168 teachers drawn from 42 sampled schools (20 public and 24 private) across Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue state using hat and draw method. This method enables all teachers in the selected schools to have equal opportunities of being used for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Chi-square (χ^2) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The choice of chi-square was informed by the fact data collected were in frequency form and mutually exclusive. This is accordance with Emaikwu (2013) that chi-square test is a non-parametric inferential statistical method used in analysis of frequencies or nominal data. As a non-parametric statistic, it makes no restrictive assumption about the distribution of scores and it can be used where the assumptions of parametric statistics about the distribution are not satisfied. For the research questions, cut-off point of 2.50 was used for decision-making arising from the analysis. The decision rule was that null hypothesis was rejected if the calculated value was less than or equal to the critical or table value and not rejected if otherwise.

Results and Discussion

Results are presented according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One: How would staff development programmes influence male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation Influence of Staff Development Programmes on Male Teachers' Self-efficacy towards Teaching at Upper Basic Education

S/No	Items	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1.	What I have learnt during staff development programme has helped me to feel confident to ask students questions during lessons.	96	2.76	1.74	Agreed
2.	Despite what I have learnt during staff development programme, I still believe that I cannot teach all the topics in my subject.	96	3.59	1.64	Agreed
3.	Even after attending staff development programme, I still lack confidence when I am teaching.	96	3.47	1.70	Agreed
4.	What I have learnt during Staff development programme has helped me to believe that I can provide an alternative examples when students are confused during lessons.	96	2.63	1.68	Agreed
5.	After attending staff development programme, I believe that I can set good questions for students during examination.	96	1.58	1.64	Disagreed

6. Staff development programme has made me to believe I can motivate students who show low interest in learning.	96	2.67	1.68	Agreed
7. What I have learnt during staff development programme has helped me to feel confident that I can make students to believe they can do well.				
8. I enjoyed taking part in staff development programme as it has assisted me to believe that I can help students to value learning.	96	2.57	1.63	Agreed
	96	3.38	1.57	Agreed
9. After staff development programme, I feel confident that I can control disruptive behaviour during lessons.	96	2.51	1.64	Agreed
10. What I learnt during staff development programme has made me to believe I can establish effective classroom management system in a class.	96	1.57	1.6	Disagreed
11. I believe I cannot cover all topics for the class I am teaching despite what I have learnt during staff development programme.	96	1.71	1.72	Disagreed
12. What I learnt during staff development programme has made me to believe I can teach effectively.	96	2.50	1.63	Agreed
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation	96	2.58	1.66	Agreed

Table 1 indicates that eleven out of the twelve items had mean rating above the bench mark mean of 2.50 which indicates that staff development programmes has positively influence male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. The analysis also reveals that three out of the twelve items had mean rating below the bench mark mean of 2.50 which shows that that staff development programmes has positively influences male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. The cluster mean rating of 2.58 implies that that staff development programmes has positively influence male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Influence of Staff Development Programmes on Female Teachers' Self-efficacy towards Teaching at Upper Basic Education

S/NO	Items	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1.	What I have learnt during staff development programme has helped me to feel confident to ask students questions during lessons.	72	2.78	1.81	Agreed
2.	Despite what I have learnt during staff development programme, I still believe that I cannot teach all the topics in my subject.	72	2.60	1.65	Agreed
3.	Even after attending staff development programme, I still lack confident when I am teaching.	72	1.50	1.72	Disagreed
4.	What I have learnt during Staff development programme has helped me to believe that I can provide an alternative example when students are confused during lessons.	72	3.61	1.69	Agreed
5.	After attending staff development programme, I believe that I can set good questions for students during examination.	72	3.59	1.66	Agreed
6.	Staff development programme has made me to believe I can motivate students who show low interest in learning.	72	2.68	1.69	Agreed
7.	What I have learnt during staff development programme has helped me to feel confident that I can make students to believe they can do well.	72	2.57	1.63	Agreed
8.	I enjoyed taking part in staff development programme as it has assisted me to believe that I can help students to value learning.	72	1.39	1.57	Disagreed
9.	After staff development programme, I feel confident that I can control disruptive behaviour during lessons.	72	1.53	1.67	Disagreed
10.	What I learnt during staff development programme has made me to believe I can establish effective classroom management system in a class.	72	2.59	1.67	Agreed
11.	I believe I cannot cover all topics for the class I am teaching despite what I have learnt during staff development programme.	72	2.75	1.77	Agreed
12.	What I learnt during staff development programme has made me to believe I can teach effectively.	72	3.54	1.69	Agreed
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		72	2.59	1.69	Agreed

Table 2 indicates that eleven out of the twelve items had mean rating above the bench mark mean of 2.50 which indicates that staff development programmes has positively influence female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. The analysis also reveals that three out of the twelve

items had mean rating below the bench mark mean of 2.50 which shows that that staff development programmes has positively influences female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. The cluster mean rating of 2.58 means that that staff development programmes has positively influence female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant of staff development programmes on male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education.

Table 3. Chi-square Test for Influence of Staff Development Programmes on Male Teachers' Self-efficacy towards Teaching

Responses	Observed frequency	Expected frequency	Chi-square	df	P-value
SA	53	52.3	90.92	33	0.00
A	31	52.3			
SD	3	52.3			
D	5	52.2			
Total	92				

Table 3 revealed X^2 of 90.92 df= 33, and P-value= 0.00. Since P-value $0.00 < 0.05$ level of significance, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of staff development programmes on male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. was rejected. This means that there is a significant influence of staff development programmes on male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education

Table 4. Chi-square Test for Influence of Staff Development Programmes on Female Teachers' Self-efficacy towards Teaching

Responses	Observed frequency	Expected frequency	Chi-square	df	P-value
SA	12	46.5	85.09	33	0.00
A	43	46.5			
SD	9	46.5			
D	4	46.5			
Total	68				

Table 4 revealed X^2 of 85.09, $df= 33$, and $P\text{-value}= 0.00$. Since $P\text{-value } 0.00 < 0.05$ level of significance, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education was rejected. This implies that there is a significant influence of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one and hypothesis one investigated whether staff development programmes influence male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. Table 1 indicated that staff development programmes influence male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. The result in Table 3 revealed a significant influence of staff development programmes on male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. This means that staff of development programmes enhances teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching.

This finding is in agreement with the earlier findings of Karabiyik and Korumaz (2014) and Karimi (2011). These researchers found in their separate studies a significant influence of staff development programmes on male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching. However, the finding of the present study disagrees which Odanga, Raburu and Aloka's (2020) study which revealed no significant influence of gender on teachers' self-efficacy.

Research question two and hypothesis two sought to determine whether staff development programmes influence female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. Table 2 showed that staff development programmes influence male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching. A significant influence of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education was found upon further analysis using Chi-square in Table 4. This implies that staff development programmes enhanced female female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching. Karimi (2011) reported that Staff professional development programme created some belief in the teachers' capabilities and was compelling enough to significantly disrupt the teachers' previous beliefs in their abilities irrespective of gender. Odanga, Raburu and Aloka's (2020) study reported no significant influence of gender on teachers' self-efficacy.

This finding agrees with Karabyik and Korumaz (2014) who found a significant influence of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching. The finding of the present study also confirms Karimi's (2011) result which showed staff professional development programme created some belief in the teachers' capabilities and was compelling enough to significantly disrupt the teachers' previous beliefs in their abilities irrespective of gender. Odanga, Raburu and Aloka's (2020) study reported no significant influence of gender on teachers' self-efficacy.

Conclusion

This study examined the effect of staff development programmes on gender of teachers for self efficacy in upper basic education in Makurdi. Results reveal that there is a significant influence of staff development programmes on male teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education. This means that staff development programmes enhance teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching. Furthermore, findings show that significant influence of staff development programmes on female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching at upper basic education was found upon further analysis. This implies that staff development programmes enhanced female teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching. Overall, the study posits that staff development programmes enhance teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching irrespective of gender and as such, it was recommended among others that state and federal Governments, non-governmental organizations, proprietors of schools and other educational stakeholders should regularize the conduct of educational conferences, workshops; seminars etc. for upper basic school teachers. This will improve teachers' efficacy, skills, productivity and effectiveness in service delivery and a sustained achievement of desired education.

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